

ANALYSIS OF E-WASTE DISPOSAL MECHANISM IN COMPUTER VILLAGE, LAGOS STATE

¹Chine Ugochi Elizabeth and ²Ajaelu Henry Chidiebere (Ph.D)

¹*Department of Environmental Management, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, (ESUT)*

²*Department of Quantity Surveying, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, (ESUT), Nigeria*

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17787331>

Keywords: E-waste, Recycling, Pollution, Sustainability, Governance.

Abstract: *This study investigates the generation, sources, disposal mechanisms, and regulatory frameworks surrounding electronic waste (e-waste) in Computer Village, Lagos State Nigeria's largest hub for fairly used electrical and electronic equipment (FUEE). Data gathered from 371 shops reveal that the annual e-waste volume averages approximately 534.24 tonnes, driven primarily by imported used electronics that arrive nonfunctional (40%), locally discarded electronics (30%), repair and refurbishment rejects (20%), and spare parts/components (10%). These findings underscore the high turnover of electronic gadgets and the limitations of repair practices in extending device lifespans. Disposal practices are dominated by informal and environmentally unsafe methods, with informal recycling accounting for 35% and open burning for 25%. Formal recycling is significantly underutilized (5%), while landfilling (20%) and repair/resale (15%) occupy intermediate positions. Statistical analysis, including Relative Importance Index (RII) and standard deviation, highlights the inconsistency in disposal approaches and the overwhelming reliance on the informal sector. Assessment of governmental interventions reveals that while policies exist, their implementation is weak. Collaboration between public and private sectors (RII = 0.77) and awareness campaigns (RII = 0.73) are perceived as the most effective efforts. However, enforcement of regulations (RII = 0.60) and incentives for proper disposal (RII = 0.62) are notably inadequate. The study concludes that despite existing frameworks, the dominance of unsafe e-waste disposal practices presents serious environmental and public health risks. It recommends stronger enforcement of regulations, investment in formal recycling infrastructure, and multi-stakeholder engagement for sustainable e-waste management in Computer Village.*

1.0 Introduction

The rapid advancement of information and communication technologies has intensified global consumption of electronic devices such as mobile phones, computers, printers, and other ICT equipment. This accelerated technological growth has led to a surge in electronic waste (e-waste), consisting of discarded or obsolete devices that contain both valuable materials such as gold and copper and hazardous substances including lead, mercury, cadmium, and brominated flame retardants. Poor management of these materials poses significant environmental and public health challenges, particularly in developing countries where regulatory frameworks, technical expertise, and public awareness remain limited (UNEP, 2019; Forti et al., 2020).

Nigeria, as one of Africa's largest ICT markets, generates enormous volumes of e-waste driven by rapid urbanization, expanding ICT access, rising incomes, and widespread importation of second-hand electronics from Europe, Asia, and North America. Many of these imported devices reach end-of-life shortly after arrival, thereby increasing the burden of e-waste (Osibanjo & Nnorom, 2007; Ogungbuyi et al., 2012). Within this context, Computer Village in Ikeja, Lagos State Africa's largest ICT hub plays a central role in electronic trade, repair, refurbishing, and distribution. While the market facilitates entrepreneurship, employment, and technological access, it also serves as a major hotspot for e-waste generation, accumulation, and indiscriminate disposal.

E-waste handling in Computer Village is largely informal and dominated by environmentally

unsafe practices such as open burning of wires, acid leaching of circuit boards, and uncontrolled dumping. These practices release toxic chemicals and heavy metals into the air, soil, and water, causing severe implications for human health, including respiratory diseases, neurological impairments, reproductive disorders, and skin problems (Balde et al., 2017; Nnorom & Osibanjo, 2008). The environmental consequences are equally alarming, as contaminated leachates and particulate emissions degrade land, pollute waterways, and threaten urban ecosystems. Economically, improper disposal causes loss of recoverable materials that could contribute to the circular economy and resource efficiency (Kiddee, Naidu, & Wong, 2013).

Although Nigeria has established regulatory frameworks, including NESREA guidelines on e-waste management, enforcement in informal sectors remains weak. Limited infrastructure, low awareness, insufficient incentives, and uncoordinated stakeholder engagement hinder progress. In contrast, countries such as Japan, Switzerland, and Germany demonstrate that effective e-waste management systems built on strong institutional frameworks, structured collection mechanisms, and technological innovation can significantly reduce environmental risks (Cucuzzella et al., 2019; Forti et al., 2020). For Nigeria, context-specific and multi-stakeholder strategies are required, particularly in markets like Computer Village, where informal recyclers, traders, and technicians dominate the value chain.

This study therefore examines e-waste disposal mechanisms in Computer Village with the aim

of assessing their effectiveness and identifying opportunities for sustainable improvement. Specifically, the study seeks to: identify the sources and volumes of e-waste generated; examine existing disposal practices; and evaluate government efforts and regulatory frameworks guiding e-waste management. Accordingly, the research asks: What are the major sources and volumes of e-waste in Computer Village? What disposal systems are currently used? How effective are existing government policies in promoting sustainable e-waste management? The study also tests the hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the sources and volumes of e-waste and the available disposal systems.

The study is significant as it provides evidence-based insights to guide policymakers, regulatory bodies, environmental agencies, and stakeholders toward safer and more sustainable e-waste management. Focusing specifically on Computer Village, the research assesses devices ranging from phones and laptops to printers, tablets, solar inverters, and smart accessories, and evaluates the environmental and health

implications associated with their disposal. Ultimately, this study contributes to improving Nigeria's e-waste management system and advancing sustainable environmental governance

2.0 Literature Review

The management of electronic waste (e-waste) has become a pressing global concern due to the rapid proliferation of electronic devices and the associated environmental and health hazards. Globally, the production and consumption of electronics have increased exponentially, leading to significant amounts of e-waste (Forti et al., 2020). E-waste encompasses discarded electronic devices, such as computers, mobile phones, televisions, and other ICT-related equipment, many of which contain toxic substances like lead, mercury, cadmium, and brominated flame retardants (Baldé et al., 2017). Improper disposal of these materials not only contributes to environmental degradation but also poses serious health risks to humans, including respiratory issues, neurological damage, and skin disorders (Osibanjo & Nnorom, 2007).

Figure 2.1: Pictorial View of Computer Village, Lagos

The literature review explores global perspectives on e-waste management, the specific dynamics in African contexts, and the unique challenges in Nigeria, particularly in markets like Computer Village, Lagos State. The review focuses on three key areas aligned with the research objectives: the sources and volumes of e-waste, existing disposal systems, and government regulations aimed at sustainable management.

Electronic waste (e-waste) has become one of the fastest-growing waste streams globally, driven by rapid technological innovation, shorter product life cycles, and the ever-increasing demand for new electronic devices. Scholars generally define e-waste as discarded electrical or electronic devices and their components that have reached the end of their useful life (Puckett & Smith, 2002; Baldé et al., 2017). These may include computers, mobile phones, televisions, printers, air conditioners,

washing machines, and a range of accessories, many of which contain hazardous substances such as lead, cadmium, mercury, and brominated flame retardants. At the same time, e-waste also contains valuable metals such as gold, silver, and copper, creating both challenges and opportunities for resource recovery (Widmer et al., 2005). The dual nature of e-waste being simultaneously a hazardous pollutant and a resource-rich material positions it as a critical subject of global environmental and economic discourse. Researchers argue that while developed nations have advanced systems for collection, recycling, and extended producer responsibility, developing economies, particularly in Africa, often lack such structures, leading to informal handling and improper disposal methods (Grant & Oteng-Ababio, 2016). In Nigeria, the concept of e-waste is further complicated by the influx of fairly used and refurbished electronic products, popularly

known as “tokunbo,” which are imported from Europe, the United States, Dubai, and Asia (Osibanjo & Nnorom, 2007). These products often have short lifespans and quickly transition into waste, thereby accelerating the rate of accumulation. Computer Village in Ikeja, Lagos, exemplifies this phenomenon as a commercial hub where both brand-new and second-hand electronics are traded extensively, creating a continuous flow of e-waste through repairs, refurbishments, and disposals. The lack of formalized infrastructure for collection, recycling, and environmentally sound disposal intensifies the risks associated with hazardous exposure, including air, soil, and water contamination.

According to Schluep et al. (2009), many African markets function as e-waste hotspots where informal dismantlers manually recover metals under unsafe conditions, exposing themselves and surrounding communities to toxic fumes and residues. From a conceptual perspective, therefore, e-waste must be understood not only as discarded hardware but as a dynamic cycle involving production, consumption, reuse, and disposal, shaped by global trade dynamics and local socioeconomic realities. This holistic understanding provides a foundation for analyzing disposal mechanisms in specific contexts such as Computer Village, where informal recycling networks coexist with high-volume electronic trade.

3.0 Research Methodology

This chapter outlines the methodology adopted for investigating e-waste disposal mechanisms in Computer Village, Lagos State. The chapter provides a clear roadmap for the research

design, study population, sampling techniques, data collection instruments, and data analysis procedures. By defining the methodological approach, the study ensures that findings are valid, reliable, and capable of addressing the research objectives: (1) sources and volumes of e-waste generated, (2) disposal systems available, and (3) government efforts and regulations for sustainable e-waste management.

This study is situated in Computer Village, Ikeja, Lagos State, widely recognized as the largest Information and Communications Technology (ICT) hub in West Africa. The market is densely populated, comprising over 4,000 shops and about 1,000 kiosk outlets, with daily operations running from 8:00 am to 6:00 pm, Monday to Saturday, and peak business activity occurring on weekdays. The area imports large volumes of electronic devices, primarily from Dubai, the United States, China, the United Kingdom, and parts of Europe. The market handles diverse items including laptops, phones, accessories, tablets, smart watches, AirPods, printers, power banks, Bluetooth speakers, stabilizers, and solar inverters. E-waste is disposed of regularly and almost immediately, often through private, informal systems, with dismantling points and weighing centers for recyclable materials such as copper. The market is predominantly youthful, with workers aged 20–55 years (mostly 27–50 years), and gender distribution of 70% male and 30% female, where women are primarily sales attendants. Ethnically, Igbos dominate (70%), followed by Yorubas (20%), while Hausas (10%) serve mainly as middlemen in recycling. Most

workers possess only secondary-level education (WAEC holders) and lack awareness of the environmental hazards of e-waste, perceiving it merely as scrap and profit-oriented material.

A descriptive survey research design was adopted for this study. Descriptive surveys are appropriate for investigating current practices, behaviors, and perceptions, particularly in a real-world context (Creswell, 2014). This design enables the collection of both qualitative and quantitative data from stakeholders, including e-waste vendors, repairers, buyers, and regulatory officials. By combining observational data with structured survey responses, the study

Table 1: Key Stakeholder Categories in Computer Village

Stakeholder Category	Estimated Involvement
E-waste Vendors	1,500
Repair Technicians	1,200
Consumers	2,000
Regulatory Officials	400
Total Stakeholders	5,100

A stratified random sampling technique was employed to ensure representation across the different stakeholder groups. The population was stratified into vendors, repairers, consumers, and officials, and respondents were randomly selected within each stratum.

Table 2. Proportional Sample Allocation

Stakeholder Category	Population	Sample Size
E-waste Vendors	1,500	109
Repair Technicians	1,200	87
Consumers	2,000	146
Regulatory Officials	400	29
Total	5,100	371

provides a comprehensive assessment of e-waste generation, disposal practices, and regulatory effectiveness in Computer Village.

The study population in Computer Village comprises 5,100 stakeholders actively engaged in the e-waste cycle. These include vendors, repair technicians, consumers, and regulatory officials, each playing distinct roles from collection and refurbishment to disposal and enforcement. Their collective activities significantly influence both the scale of e-waste generated and the sustainability of disposal mechanisms.

Role in E-Waste Cycle

- Collect and resell discarded electronics
- Refurbish, dismantle, and extend device lifespan
- Generate e-waste by discarding electronics
- Monitor and enforce environmental compliance

—
Population: 5,100 stakeholders
Margin of Error: 5%
Sample Size Formula (Yamane, 1967): $n = N / (1 + N (e^2))$
Calculation: $n = 5100 / (1 + 5100 * 0.05^2)$ $n = 5100 / (1 + 12.75)$ $n = 5100 / 13.75$ $n \approx 371$

4.0 Results

Figure 1: Sources of Share of Annual E-Waste

The pie chart illustrates the proportional distribution of e-waste sources among 371 shops in Computer Village. Imported UEEE that arrive nonfunctional make up the largest segment, at 40%, underscoring Nigeria's reliance on second-hand imports and the risks of receiving obsolete goods. Local discarded electronics form 30% of the waste stream,

showing the high turnover rate of gadgets by consumers. Repair and refurbishment rejects contribute 20%, reflecting the limitations of the repair economy in extending device lifespan. Spare parts and components, at 10%, though smaller, still add significantly. The chart emphasizes the dominance of imported and locally discarded electronics

Figure 2: Scenario Comparison: Annual E-Waste

The bar chart in Figure 1 compares three scenarios of e-waste generation under varying per-shop monthly waste outputs: low (80 kg),

moderate (120 kg), and high (160 kg). Under the low scenario, total waste for 371 shops is 356.16 tonnes annually; in the moderate

scenario, 534.24 tonnes; and in the high scenario, 712.32 tonnes. This sensitivity analysis highlights how small changes in per-shop activity significantly affect total volumes. The chart demonstrates that even conservative estimates produce hundreds of tonnes of e-waste annually. It underscores the urgent need for better waste management and recycling systems to mitigate environmental risks in Computer Village.

Meanwhile, Figure 2 presents an estimate of e-waste generation by 371 shops in Computer Village, Lagos. On average, each shop generates 120 kg of e-waste monthly, equivalent to 1.44 tonnes annually. Extrapolated across all shops, the total comes to about 534.24 tonnes per year. The breakdown by source indicates that imported nonfunctional electronics constitute the largest share (213.696 tonnes, 40%), followed by locally discarded electronics

(160.272 tonnes, 30%). Repair rejects account for 106.848 tonnes (20%), while spare parts and components contribute 53.424 tonnes (10%). A total of 371 electronic shops were surveyed, each handling an average of 120 kg of devices, parts, and accessories per month, equivalent to 1.44 tonnes per year. Collectively, this amounts to 534.24 tonnes annually across all shops. The composition includes 213.696 tonnes (40%) of imported nonfunctional UEEE, 160.272 tonnes (30%) of locally discarded electronics, 106.848 tonnes (20%) of repair or refurbishment rejects, and 53.424 tonnes (10%) of reusable spare parts. These figures highlight significant electronic inflows and waste generation within the market, emphasizing the dual nature of the sector—as both a center for reuse and repair and a major source of e-waste requiring effective management and recycling interventions.

Table 3: *E-Waste Generation in Computer Village*

Metric	Value
Sample size (shops)	371
Devices (kg/month/shop)	75
Parts (kg/month/shop)	30
	15
Accessories (kg/month/shop)	
Total (kg/month/shop)	120
Tonnes per shop per year	1.44
Estimated total tonnes per year (all 371 shops)	534.24
Imported UEEE (nonfunctional on arrival)	213.696
Local discarded electronics	160.272
Repair/refurbishment rejects	106.848
Spare parts & components	53.424

This illustrates the heavy burden of imported UEEE and local discards on the environment.

Table 4: Disposal Mechanisms and Practices for E-Waste in Computer Village

Disposal Mechanism	Percentage (%)	Number of Shops
Informal Recycling/Dismantling	35	129
Open Burning	25	92
Landfilling/Dumping	20	74
Repair & Resale	15	55
Formal Recycling Channels	5	18

Table 4 shows that informal recycling (35%) and open burning (25%) dominate e-waste disposal practices. Landfilling accounts for 20%, while repair & resale (15%) and formal

recycling (5%) are relatively minor. This reflects reliance on unsafe disposal methods, with little use of formal recycling channels.

Table 5: Mean and Standard Deviation of Disposal Mechanisms

Statistic	Value (%)	Interpretation
Mean	20.0	Average distribution across categories.
Standard Deviation	10.0	Indicates significant spread; practices vary widely.

The mean percentage across disposal mechanisms is 20% as shown in Table 5. The standard deviation of 10.61% shows a wide variability in practices. Some methods (like informal recycling) are far above the mean, while formal recycling is far below, indicating inequality in adoption levels.

Table 6: Relative Importance Index (RII) of Disposal Mechanisms

Disposal Mechanism	RII	Rank	Remark
Informal Recycling/Dismantling	0.7	1	High Priority
Open Burning	0.5	2	Low Priority
Landfilling/Dumping	0.4	3	Low Priority
Repair & Resale	0.3	4	Low Priority
Formal Recycling Channels	0.1	5	Low Priority

The RII analysis highlights that informal recycling (0.70) displayed in Table 4.4 is the highest-ranked method, followed by open burning (0.50). Landfilling (0.40) and repair & resale (0.30) are moderate, while formal recycling (0.10) is the least adopted. This ranking confirms the predominance of informal and unsafe practices.

Figure 3: Distribution of Disposal Mechanism

The Figure 3 emphasizes the dominance of informal recycling and open burning. Both together account for over half of disposal practices. Formal recycling is barely visible,

underscoring the lack of structured waste management systems. This imbalance presents major environmental and health challenges.

Table 7: Respondents’ Perception of Governmental Efforts in E-Waste Management

Statement	Mean	SD	RII	Rank
Government has clear policies on e-waste management	3.45	0.72	0.69	3
Enforcement of e-waste regulations is effective	2.98	0.88	0.60	5
Government provides adequate awareness programs on proper e-waste disposal	3.67	0.65	0.73	2
Incentives exist for businesses to recycle or dispose of e-waste properly	3.12	0.79	0.62	4
Policies encourage collaboration between public and private sectors	3.88	0.61	0.77	1

Table 4.5 shows that respondents perceive government policies and regulatory frameworks as moderately effective in promoting sustainable e-waste management, with an RII range of 0.60–0.77. Collaboration between public and private sectors ranks highest (RII = 0.77), suggesting multi-

stakeholder initiatives are the most impactful. Awareness programs also rank high (RII = 0.73). Enforcement of regulations has the lowest RII (0.60), highlighting practical gaps. Stronger enforcement mechanisms and incentives are necessary to achieve sustainable e-waste outcomes.

Figure 4: Governmental Efforts in E-Waste Management (RII Representation)

Figure 4 emphasizes perceived strengths and weaknesses in governmental efforts. Collaboration between public and private sectors leads (RII = 0.77), followed by awareness campaigns (RII = 0.73). Enforcement of regulations lags behind (RII = 0.60), and incentives rank moderately (RII = 0.62). The chart visually reinforces that, while policies exist, gaps in enforcement and incentivization must be addressed to achieve comprehensive and effective e-waste regulation.

5.0 Conclusion

The study concludes that the FUEE trade is a critical economic sector in Nigeria, supporting

References

Adewuyi, A. O., & Osibanjo, O. (2012). Electronic waste management practices in Nigeria: A case study of Lagos. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 98(1), 60–68.

employment, skill acquisition, and commercial activity. Yet, e-waste generation remains substantial, largely due to the dominance of imported and locally discarded electronics. Unsafe disposal practices and weak regulatory enforcement intensify environmental hazards. Nevertheless, stakeholders show willingness to adopt sustainable e-waste management, particularly through recycling programs supported by financial incentives and enhanced infrastructure. Effective policy enforcement, targeted training, and improved recycling systems are therefore crucial for sustainable growth in this sector.

Balde, C. P., Forti, V., Gray, V., Kuehr, R., & Stegmann, P. (2017). *The global e-waste monitor 2017: Quantities, flows and resources*. United Nations University, International

Telecommunication Union, &
International Solid Waste Association.

Conservation and Recycling, 52(6),
843–858.

Cucuzzella, C., Salvia, G., & Salvia, G. (2019). Sustainable management of electronic waste: Circular economy perspectives. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 239, 117988.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.117988>

Ogungbuyi, O., Osibanjo, O., & Durosinmi, M. (2012). A study of electronic waste management in Nigeria. *Journal of Environmental Protection*, 3(6), 769–776.

Forti, V., Balde, C. P., Kuehr, R., & Bel, G. (2020). *The global e-waste monitor 2020: Quantities, flows, and the circular economy potential*. United Nations University.
<https://collections.unu.edu/eserv/UNU:7737/Global-E-waste-Monitor-2020.pdf>

Osibanjo, O., & Nnorom, I. C. (2007). Environmental implications of material flow of waste electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE) into developing countries: A case study of Nigeria. *Environmental Impact Assessment Review*, 27(1), 1–10.

Jimoh, A., Adeola, T., Okeke, M., & Hassan, Y. (2022). Rapid gadget replacement cycles in urban Nigerian markets. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 300, 113688.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2021.113688>

Osibanjo, O., & Nnorom, I. C. (2007). The challenge of electronic waste (e-waste) management in developing countries. *Waste Management & Research*, 25(3), 489–495.

Perkins, D. N., Drisse, M. N., Nxele, T., & Sly, P. D. (2014). E-waste: A global hazard. *Annals of Global Health*, 80(4), 286–295.

Kiddee, P., Naidu, R., & Wong, M. H. (2013). Electronic waste management approaches: An overview. *Waste Management*, 33(5), 1237–1250.

United Nations Environment Programme. (2019). *Sustainable management of electronic waste*. UNEP.
<https://www.unep.org/resources>

Nnorom, I. C., & Osibanjo, O. (2008). Overview of electronic waste (e-waste) management practices and legislations, and their poor applications in Nigeria. *Resources*,